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ABSTRACT

Rotavirus and invasive meningococcal infections are major causes of morbidity and hospital admissions among infants and young children. Vaccination remains the most effective preventive measure against both diseases. Rotavirus vaccines significantly reduce severe gastroenteritis and associated healthcare burden, while meningococcal conjugate and recombinant vaccines offer long-lasting protection against life-threatening meningitis and sepsis (Akdeniz & Erkek, 2016; Carvalho & Gill, 2019).

Family physicians play a critical role in implementing national immunization programs. They are well-positioned to educate caregivers, address vaccine hesitancy, and ensure timely administration during routine well-child visits. Conjugate meningococcal vaccines (MenACWY) induce strong immune responses in all age groups and reduce bacterial carriage, supporting herd immunity. Recombinant MenB vaccines, developed through genomic sequencing, provide protection against serogroup B, which presents unique immunological challenges (Akdeniz & Erkek, 2016; Hollingshead & Tang, 2019).

This presentation highlights current vaccine recommendations, safety profiles, and implementation strategies in primary care. Promoting both rotavirus and meningococcal vaccinations can significantly reduce disease burden and contribute to the WHO's global goals for meningitis elimination by 2030. Equipping family physicians with up-to-date knowledge ensures effective communication with families and strengthens routine immunization coverage in early childhood.

KEYWORDS

Rotavirus, meningococ, vaccine

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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